

**INFLUENCE OF FIELD TRIP IN TEACHING AND LEARNING
OF BIOLOGY AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN
EZINIHITE MBAISE LGA**

BY

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this research work titled “Influence of field trip in Teaching and Learning of Biology among Secondary School Students in Ezinihitte Mbaise LGA” was written by Enyiason Commissioner C. (17/39440) and has not been submitted or received anywhere for the purpose of acquiring a degree in Education/Biology.

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APPROVAL PAGE

This research project “Influence of Field Trip in Teaching and Learning of Biology among Secondary School Students in Ezinihittte Mbaise LGA” was carried out by Enyiason Commissioner C. of the Department of Life Science Education in the Faculty of Education, Imo State University, Owerri and is read and approved by:

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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to God Almighty for His infinite mercies, to my wonderful parents, Hon. Chief and Lolo E.C. Enyiason, and to my beloved siblings for their love and support.

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ABSTRACT

This study was designed to investigate the influence of field trips on the teaching and learning of biology among secondary school students in Ezinihitte Mbaise LGA, Imo State. The research was guided by four research questions and adopted a descriptive research design. The sample for the study consisted of 436 students, representing 10% of the population, selected from 11 government schools in the Local Government Area using a simple random sampling technique.

A 16-item modified 4-point rating scale, constructed by the researcher, was used to collect data for answering the research questions. The instrument was validated by a specialist in Education and Measurement and Evaluation. Mean scores were used to analyse the data and answer the research questions. The mean of item scores for all data collected ranged from 3.0 to 3.2.

The study found, among other things, that field trips help biology students understand concepts faster, as they provide firsthand knowledge and experience. In view of this, the researcher recommended, among others, that the government should include field trips in the school curriculum to help develop a positive attitude towards them. Additionally, timetable planners should allocate adequate time for field trips.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

The researcher in this chapter discusses the background to the study, statement of the problem, scope of the study, purpose of the study, significance of the study and research questions.

Background to the Study

Biology is basically the study of life. It is a natural science that focuses on the study of living organisms, including their structures, functions, development, interactions, evolution, distribution, and taxonomy. The scope of the field is extensive and is divided into several specialized disciplines, such as: anatomy, physiology, entomology, genetics, and many more.

Biology is subdivided into separate branches for convenience of study - plants (botany), animals (zoology), and the study of the structure of organisms (morphology). The study of biology helps us to understand nature; Studying different parts of an animal/plant helps us to understand the mechanisms in action in many processes, such as reproduction, metabolism, food collection, behavior etc. It also helps us understand many aspects of animals/plants. Teaching and learning of biology should be based on observation, and experiments that will make the course interesting. Field trips are therefore vital

as it opens up opportunities for students and teachers to learn together outside the classroom instead of continuous classroom work (Uwabuike, 2013).

Biology ranges from microscopic cellular molecules to the biosphere encompassing the earth's surface and its living organisms.

Biology, with its scientific method, investigates inquiries that arise from an observed phenomenon. It tries to make observations, put forward possible hypotheses to account for observation, design, and conduct experiments to test hypotheses, analyze results and draw conclusions. Accept, reject or modify hypothesis, share results (Ango, 2003).

Primarily, field trips are seen as a support for effective teaching and not a center of attention. Awotua-Efabo (2009) argued effective teaching as getting the content (message) across in a manner that will accomplish the desired objectives, and add also if at the end of the instruction the student do what the teacher wants them to do through the process of evaluation, then effective teaching has taken place.

Furthermore, Biology field trips by secondary school students are expected to enhance students' learning experience through interaction with resource persons and the environment. Rickinson (2004) asserts that field trips can lead to life-defining decisions. It can help to broaden horizons, both literally and educationally and offers great potential for personal development, building

independence, self esteem, self confidence and team work. Such potential life-defining opportunities for biologists need to be celebrated and nurtured. Whilst attention often focuses on pressures and demands, field activities can be highly effective in developing natural understanding between teachers and students which enhances the effectiveness of learning and can provide motivation which transfers/remains after the field experience.

Concepts of Field Trip strategy was introduced in 1827 by George Shillibeer for a Quaker school at Abney Park in Stoke Newington, London, United Kingdom. A field trip is a visit to a place outside the regular classroom which is designed to achieve certain objectives, which cannot be achieved as well by using other means. For example if the lesson is on “making cheese”, and if there is no hands- on experience it is very difficult to achieve the objectives. In such a lesson this strategy is required. Field trips give opportunities for students to get out of the classroom and experience something new. The location for field trips can be zoos, colleges, museums, theater and schools. Features of field trips facilitate the learning of abstract concepts. Taking students on a field trip makes learning more effective as they will be able to gain vast ideas on the topic. Motivate students through increased interest and curiosity. Field trips can add variety to the regular classroom instructional program and they tend to be special and enjoyable learning experiences. As a result, students will develop

positive attitudes in students toward related classroom activities. Increases student-student and student-teacher social interaction. Field trips provide an opportunity to involve students, parents, and the teachers in the instructional program. Students can select the place to be visited, developing questions to ask, writing reports or thank you letters after the trip, or evaluating the experiences. Since parents must give their permission, a letter sent home with the permission from explaining the purpose of the trip is a good way to arouse their curiosity and encourage them to ask the student or teacher about the trip. The parent guides their child in order to make sure that they do not come to any harm. This role allows the parent and teacher to establish a much closer relationship. The interaction between students within themselves will also be increased when they work in groups. Moreover, the interaction between the students and teacher will enhance as the students will have to discuss with the teachers when they have doubts. Develops social awareness. Field trips make students aware of learning activities in everyday life. For instance, visits to supermarkets or shopping malls are typical field experiences, which teachers may fail to notice. A well-organized trip to a "normal" place is an excellent method of teaching students to observe, ask questions, and learn in the large classroom. [See supporting study on grossarchive.](#)

The field trip is normally student centered. It promotes discovery learning and enables students to interact with the external environment and gives them opportunity to explore the environment and encourages permanent extension of knowledge. This is simple because students remember easily what they see, touch, and feel rather than abstract facts. Based on the above expository, the study on “Influence of Field Trip in Teaching and Learning of Biology among Secondary School Students in Ezinihitte Mbaise L.G.A” is needed.

Statement of the Problem

It has been observed that most students describe certain physical and observable natural phenomena, even when they have no practical knowledge and experience over them. For instance many describe structure, colour, sizes of different species of plants and animals but fail to identify them when closely examined.

Perrot (2003) states that many students express that learning of biology will be more interesting if they were allowed to have first hand information and facilitate effective learning of the subject. A trip to museums, geological areas, zoos, factories etc, expands students' learning through active hands-on experience with the rich resource of nature. This method in teaching and learning of biology could be influenced by many parameters which may lead to ineffective utility of the method.

Field trip, these days, is being swept under the carpet hence, teaching and learning of biology is no longer firsthand. Students are not conversant with the things they learnt. They can hardly even identify organisms when they see them in person. For this reason, it is important to bring to light the influence of field trips in teaching and learning of biology.

Scope of Study

The scope of the study is delimited to the influence of field trips in teaching and learning of biology in Ezinihitte Mbaise local Government area. It includes the senior secondary school students in the local Government Area. Specifically, the study covers exposure to the use of field trips, strategies and problems.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study is to investigate the influence of field trips in Ezinihitte Mbaise Local Government Area. Specifically, the study will do the following.

1. Find out the extent of exposure to the use of field trip in teaching and learning Biology
2. Determine the influence of field trips in Biology students' performance.
3. Identify the problems that militate against effective use of the field in teaching and learning of Biology.

4. Find out the strategies for effective use of field trips in teaching and learning of Biology.

Significance of the Study

This study will be of great benefit to Biology students, teachers, community, Government, parents, and future researchers.

The result of this study will create a positive effect on students on the use of field trips in learning of Biology because students easily remember what they see. It also gives students educational experience away from their regular school environment and gives students a welcome routine. The result of the study will help the Government to understand and accept field trips as an effective way of teaching and learning Biology. It will also help in attracting Government attention towards providing more allocation to schools and inclusion of field trips into school curriculum.

During service oriented field trips, students learn about helping others in the community. The community also benefits both from the work that students do as part of the trip and from any further volunteering that students do as a result of the trip. Teachers benefit from field trips include: hands-on real world experiences, quality of education, positive attitude of science and motivation towards the subject, etc.

Research Questions

1. To what extent are students exposed to field trips in teaching Biology?
2. What is the importance of embarking on a field trip?
3. What are the problems that militate against the use of field trips in teaching and learning of Biology?
4. What strategies can be effectively employed in the use of field trips in teaching and learning of Biology?

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The researcher in this chapter presents major concepts of the study, Theoretical Framework, Empirical Review/studies and Summary of Literature Review.

Major Concepts of the Study

Field trip

Tisher (2010) defined field trip as any planned visit outside the school premises which is set out to satisfy stated objectives, get information, collect and classify specimens. A field trip is a structured activity that occurs outside the classroom. It can be a brief observation. It is considered as one of the three avenues through which education can be handled through formal classroom teaching, practical work, and field trips.

According to Mulyasa (2005) *field trip is a journey undertaken by learners to acquire learning experience, especially direct experience and an integral part of the school curriculum.*

In America, teachers tend to use the term “field trip” rather than “excursion” because of its predominately American origin.

It has been scientifically stated that the use of field trip in educational training helps to effect the expected behavioral change in the students, therefore, the students should be taught with the most effective method of teaching the

subjects, and the field trip which according to Mbadiugha (2004) gives the students amassed information which help them solve a problem and to an area of knowledge, learn a new technique or achieved whatever his objectives was. According to Iwu (2011) field trips *involve taking the students out of the field to provide first hand information or observe organisms in their natural environment. 'Field' here can be industries, fish ponds, forest game reserves or streams. It is a good method of teaching science since it provides opportunities for students to see the realities of life.*

The advanced learners' dictionary of current English (2010) also defined it as "scientific" technical or social investigation made outside laboratories etc. Example: by survey, geologist or by students of social sciences who visit and talk to people.

Again, oxford advanced learners' dictionary international students (2011) defines field trip as a journey made by a group of people, often students, to study something in its natural environment. From the various definitions of field trip, we can know that field trip is a practical work and can be done very well outside the classroom, at least for the change of environment. Field trip is student centered whereby every student will be asked to participate actively in the lesson and not teacher centered, it also promotes discovery learning.

Field Trip and Teacher's Attitude

Field trip can be considered as one of the avenues through which science can be taught through formal classroom teaching practical work and field trip. The literature concerning field trips tends to be organized around a number of themes, not all of which are directly appropriate to the study. Much of the literature originates from museums and science centres with less from other avenues such as zoos, aquariums, planetariums, field study or nature centre weight (1992). Much of what has been written about teachers conducting field trips has been anecdotal.

Timir and Zoor (2014) reviewed texts and research articles by science educators, summarizing their reasons for taking field trips into five attributed values.

- Providing first-hand experience.
- Stimulating interest and motivation in science.
- Giving meaning to learning and interrelationship.
- Observation and perception skills.
- Person (social) development.

Quantitative studies of the attitudes of teachers towards field trip were undertaken by Crawley and Koballa (2000)

Therefore, the opinion of teachers, the positive benefits derived from field trip were:

- i. Hands on real world experiences.
- ii. Quality of education, positive attitude of science and motivation towards the subject.
- iii. Improvement of the socialization study and well developed rapport between teacher and students.
- iv. Enabling teachers to utilize other learning strategies such as cooperative learning. While the negative attitude of teachers was revealed.
- v. Difficulties with transportation, including cost.
- vi. Teacher's skills, the disparity between theory and practice and perceived teacher inertia.
- vii. Time consideration, preparation, fitting into the school time table.
- viii. Lack of support from school administration for field trips.
- ix. Curriculum inflexibility.
- x. Inadequacy of resources and choice of venue.

Needs for Field Trip

Green (2008) states that the tradition of verbal learning and memorizing has in some places led to a formal and abstract approach to science teaching as a whole, at the expense of practical work in the field.

Field trips should be done in a natural environment where the students get the first-hand experience needed for effective learning.

Nwabueze (2010) maintained that there is no substitute for the first-hand information gained through observation of the living population in diverse situations and localities. He further said that the recognition of organisms in the outdoors is a long step towards the appreciation of nature and life itself.

Students should be made to understand the real meaning of what they are taught in class by taking them into the field. The realities of living things can only be seen in their natural environment that is in the field.

Need For Inclusion of Field Trip in the School Curriculum

Field trips improve the method of teaching and learning. It will be important for curriculum planners to make field trips compulsory for all students both in the primary, secondary and tertiary institutions. The school time table planners should map out enough time for field trips, so that every teacher and students would benefit from this method.

On the side of the time table planner, it should be designed in order for it not to clash with other subjects on the time table and parents should stop objecting

their children going on field trip with the fear of them being injured, rather, they should be encouraged and motivated, Mbadiugha (2004).

It has made it often impossible for the student to grasp easily what they are taught and also made it possible for the teachers sometimes to convey adequately what they want to impact on the students. It is most disheartening that teachers are aware of the effectiveness of field trips in achieving and enhancing learning. The use of field trips have been revealed to help the students for easy exploration of their immediate environment, it gives them ample opportunity to see things for themselves in their natural environment.

It gives them new experiences whenever they embark on a field trip. It helps them to retain most of the things they are taught because they were able to see and touch most of the things. The use of field trips due to its effectiveness needs to be institutionalized in all schools, though it may be faced with some problems.

Educational Implication of Field Trip

It is obvious that field trips have an effect on teaching and learning. Inability of the teachers to make good use of field trips in teaching and learning is really affecting the educational system. Field trip is targeted at unfolding some practice which are not taught or overlooked by the lecture.

The neglect of field trips in the school has a serious effect on the students because it does not give them the opportunity to explore their immediate environment. Field trips according to some research work will improve teaching and learning. Thus, the adage “what you see is more remembered than what you hear”. So the use of field trips will help students to remember what they see whenever they are called upon because they have the opportunity to carry out some practical on most topics and this method enhances learning.

Some factors such as lack of finance, parents and teacher’s negative attitude and distance have been found to militate against the use of field trips in teaching and learning. Therefore, there is a need for these factors to be met in order to promote the use of field trips in achieving the educational goal.

Field Trip as a teaching Method in Biology

There is a wide variety of instructional techniques available for instructors to use at the college level. In addition to lectures, class discussion, laboratory activities, online teaching etc. Field trips are useful, valuable teaching tools particularly in biology.

Field experiences enhance synthesis of information, cognitive reasoning ability, self confidence, and self efficacy and research collaboration skills.

Ecology, field trip and learning of biology

Ecology has been reported as one aspect of senior secondary school biology curriculum that students find difficult to answer questions as they perform poorly in questions bothering on ecological concepts. (Eze, 2013; Okoye & Okechukwu; 2010, WAEC Chief Examiner's reports 2014, 2016, 2017 & 2018). The reason for this difficulty is either that the students lack the framework to deepen their understanding of the concepts or the use of ineffective teaching methods in teaching the concepts. Certain aspects of basic ecological concepts like population density, habitat, etc taught in secondary schools require some calculations. Such teachers and students would prefer a theoretical aspect which requires weighing and measuring. This trend has contributed to the general poor performance of candidates in question that deal with ecological concepts in the WAEC Chief Examiner's report in biology (WAEC Chief Examiner's reports 2014, 2016, 2017 & 2018). The WAEC Chief Examiner's report stated that the major reason for students' poor performance in ecology questions is their inability to apply abstract reasoning to understand concepts in ecology. The utility of ecological concepts in biology has made ecology an important topic in biology. Ecology is a very important branch of biology as it connects biology with other fields of learning such as Agriculture, Agronomy, Horticulture, and Environmental sciences. Ecology studies the interrelationships between organisms and their natural environment,

both living and non-living. It denotes that no organism can live in isolation; instead it must interact with its environment. That is to say, no plant or animal is independent of its environment. Ecology is concerned with the biology of groups of organisms with functional processes on land, in the oceans and in fresh water (Obeka, 2010). For this purpose, ecologists study organisms in the context of the populations and communities in which they can be grouped and the ecosystems of which they form part. The study of ecological interactions provides important information on the nature and mechanisms of evolutionary change. Advances made in ecology over the past decades have led to increased concern about the effects of man's activities on the environment (notably the effects of pollution), which has resulted in a greater awareness of the importance of conservation. Therefore there is a need therefore for biology teachers to get acquainted with the methods that are suitable or effective in teaching this aspect of biology called ecology. Dorgu (2015) pointed out that good teachers follow no one method, instead they use whatever methods or materials that seem best for the particular combination of individual situations. The present study will investigate the effect of field trips on academic achievement of students in ecology. Field trip teaching strategy encourages co-operation between the teacher and the learners and may improve achievement of the concept of ecology.

For effective teaching of ecology, the use of a field trip which makes use of the environment could achieve much and bring home the actual meaning of concepts. Field trip is that instructional strategy that allows students to obtain direct experience from a natural setting (Abdul, Oyeronke & Adunni, 2015). It is a visit to out of school environments in order to observe the real world and obtain some specific information. The theoretical basis for field trip is Vygotsky's Socio-cultural theory of learning "that learning takes place in a social environment."

Field trips may be referred to as trips to various places to obtain information directly by seeing things as they really are. It could be in a nearby school farm, national park, zoo, industry, forest or game reserve. Field trip is a critical component of science teaching, not a separate activity, but a direct extension of classroom instruction. That is why a quality science curriculum is one that extends beyond the walls of the classroom. Field trip is fundamental to biological studies which derive much of their impetus from the interrelationships of living organisms with themselves and their environment. Field trip is one of the most enjoyable and exciting experiences for students studying biology which has a lot to do with living organisms and their environment. This is because; it offers the learners firsthand experience of real things which cannot be brought into the classroom practically. When field trips

are undertaken by students, the main objective is to gain additional knowledge through direct experience that will bring about active learning while dealing with concrete material. The concept of field trip instruction includes field work, school excursion and garden tour. Some positive benefits derived from field trips are hands-on, real world experiences, quality education, positive attitudes to science, motivation towards the subject, development of rapport between teachers and students and many more. Through field trips, students are able to witness a real life location and view their topic subject of learning within the everyday context and these visits enable students to gain knowledge and perhaps a different perspective on their topic. It provides an opportunity for students to view information for themselves and use their own senses to touch, or feel materials that they had previously only heard about. This immediacy and accessibility is a key feature of field trips and one of its redeeming features. Leaving the school premises is a social experience and one, which provides a change of tempo and scenery for students. Field trips expose students to new experiences and can increase interest and engagement in science regardless of prior interest in a topic (Omeodu & Abara, 2018). On field trips, learners sharpen their skills of observations, perception and objective report of observations by utilizing all their senses (Shakil, Faizi & Hafeez, 2011). It makes the students more imaginative and inquest live

observers. However, there are also disadvantages that should be considered before planning for a field trip. They include lack of chaperones, students may misbehave, budget constraints, safety concerns and time management. While a field trip may be an exciting time for students and teachers, these challenges may end up making it an unpleasant experience, thereby ruining the learning experience if not properly managed by the Biology teachers and their students. This could mean that conventional lecture methods of teaching may prove more effective in improving the achievement of students in ecology. Conventional lecture method is a teacher-centered method whereby the teacher is seen as an authority imparting knowledge to the students. It could involve a mix of different methods, but it is mainly the lecture or expository methods that are commonly used. Although, conventional lecture method of teaching has been shown in a number of studies to be less effective compared to other innovative methods, teachers still adopt them for teaching and learning. This is because the conventional lecture method is suitable for teaching large groups of students and for covering large content areas. By implication, all methods of teaching science in general and biology in particular could boast the achievement and retention of biology concepts. Academic achievement is commonly measured by the means of class assignments, tests and examinations like West WAEC and National Examination Council (NECO) (Bahago & Ogaga, 2015). Scores

and grades are assigned based on the performance of students to determine whether their achievement is low or high. Academic achievement therefore, is the scholastic standing of a learner at a given moment (Adeyemi, 2010). Ezenwosu and Nworgu (2013) referred to students' achievement as the degree of success attained by students after being exposed to a specific area of study or field work. Jimoh (2014) corroborates that academic achievement is the level of success attained by students in school subjects. In other words, it is the degree of success reached in some general or specific area of study. Additionally, Bahago (2011) defined academic achievement as the learning outcomes of students from what they are taught by their teachers within the classroom. Achievement in education is directly related to knowledge retention. Retention is the ability to preserve, store and later remember information or knowledge gained after learning (Gambari, Bello, Agboola & Adeoye 2016). That is to say students' ability to retain a learned concept for future use. Learners must retain knowledge acquired during teaching/learning. Learning is said to have occurred when what is learnt remains relatively permanent in the mind of the learner. Hence, retention of what is learnt by students is very important. A learner who repeats an acquired piece of knowledge with less error is said to have retained the material learnt. Similarly, when what is learnt is not retained or fades with time learning becomes inconsistent.

Major Benefits of Field Trip as a Teaching Method include:

Observing a natural setting first-hand makes learning interesting and enjoyable, providing opportunities for students to gain field research experiences, learning through active participation and exploring practical or pressing biological and ecological issues onsite.

Furthermore, students can observe plants and animals communities occurring in natural settings that cannot be duplicated in classrooms, laboratories and green houses students can observe and appreciate naturally occurring phenomena, the diversity and complexity of local and regional ecosystem, interaction among living organisms, interaction between organisms and their immediate environments, various stages of ecological succession, how individual organisms and populations respond to environmental stress, how communities respond to various types and intensities of disturbance as well as why certain species can tolerate or recover from severe disturbance substantially more than others.

Precautions to be taken on Embarking on field Trip

Teachers should take certain precautions while carrying out field trips. Embarking on a pre-trip before the main trip is necessary. The areas should be

visited in time of investigation, when this is done, they can now inform the school authority in the area of their interest.

There is a need to carry along with them a first aid kit, so that any minor injury or health problem can be taken care of. Any trip outside the school premises requires written permission from the school authority so that in terms of accident, the teacher will not be held liable.

Theoretical Framework

Field trip is scientific in its approach. This includes observation, experimentation, research and investigation. In the process of carrying out this research, a lot of theories were found which are into existence, but only the following will be used in this work.

Gestalt – Field Theory

The theory was propounded by Kurt Lewin. It was introduced to philosophy and psychology in 1890. The theory states that behaviour is a function of a person in an environment, hence, cannot be viewed in isolation from the situation they are in.

It focuses attention on events inside the learner as well as those in the environment. Learning involves an internal reorganization of knowledge that integrates new material or experiences with materials previously learnt. It is

described as a change in the learner's knowledge, understanding or cognitive structure.

Man as an active creature, when given a stimulating environment can always manipulate the environmental variables to his desire and satisfaction to achieve his goals. This theory is related to this topic, because if man is given the opportunity to learn outside his classroom environment, he will acquire other skills that will be useful to him. (Seymour Papert and Jerome Burner)

Stimulus – Response Theory

This theory was propounded by Edwin Lee Thorndike. He first presented his theory in his book - Animal Learning, published in 1898. It states that there is a stimulus that triggers a response based on the internal feelings or behaviour of an organism (person).

Stimulus – response theory explains learning that focus on external events as the cause of changes in observable behaviors. The processes that will facilitate learning include: Enriched environments, problem solving, discovery learning, excursion, assignment, project, debates, quizzes etc.

Stimulus – response theory examines the way the learner reacts to change in his external environment, consequences of an action determines the repetition of the action that brought the consequences. This is in line with the topic as

students learn through this method, especially when they are in the field (Patrick Suppes, L. Thorndike)

Observation –Learning Theory

This can be called social learning theory. It was propounded by Albert Bandura in 1977. The theory suggests that observation and modeling play a primary role in how and why people learn. It has interactive approach to learning, the theory is based on the fact that behavior is a learned phenomenon and as a result, personality can be explained in terms of these theories to this topic is that there must be a proper interaction, observations between the students and their environment for teaching and learning to be effective (Bandura and Walter).

Review of Empirical Studies

This aspect is aimed at looking into research carried out by other researchers to ascertain if there is a significant difference or not.

Empirical studies on field trip

Nwankwo (2016) carried out a study on “field trip method in the teaching and learning biology in Mbaise”.

At the end of the work, the result of the findings shows that 30% are in support of the use of lecture methods in teaching Biology, 45% conventional method

while 85% are in support of field trip in teaching Biology. The researcher recommended that fieldwork in Biology outside the school premises should be made compulsory in secondary schools at least once a term. She also added that the federal, state, and local government, ministry of Education should arrange for transport and funds that will enhance effective use of fieldwork in Biology. Onyeka (2010) on her research, she carried out on “The use of field work in teaching and learning Biology in Isiala Mbano L.G.A”. The researcher sampled four schools and collected her data by the use of structured questionnaires and it was analyzed using simple percentages. The result of the findings revealed that 60% of the students in the field chartered for themselves, while 40% of the students were sponsored by the school. 70% of the teachers discouraged the use of field trip in teaching because it wastes time and endangers students’ life, while 97% of students advocate the use of field trip in teaching and learning of Biology because it makes them to easily remember what they are taught in the theory. Having carried out research work, the researcher came out with the following recommendations. “Teachers of Biology should be educated properly on the importance of field trips in the teaching of science, to be rooted in the minds of the learners. She also included that the school authority should provide adequate time when planning the school time table and should make provision for evening lessons for effective use of field trips.

A research work was carried on the Effects Of Educational Field Trips On Social Studies Students' Academic Achievement In Junior Secondary Schools In Kaduna State, NIGERIA by Jamilu Ja'afar Salihu, and I.D Abubakar, Department of Arts and Social Science Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria-Nigeria. In the findings, It was discovered that, who were taught using educational field trips outperformed their counterparts taught using lecture methods in junior secondary schools in Zaria Education Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria. This finding is in line with whose work found a significant difference in process of science test scores between students exposed to field trip experiences and those who were not exposed (Farmer et al., 2007; Flexer and Borun, 1984; Lisowski and Disinger, 1991; Mackenzie and White, 1982; Salihu, 2015). Educationists and philosophers emphasized more on allowing the learners to explore, inquire and find out facts by themselves under the supervision and guidance of the teacher. The teacher is the initiator of the learning process, a guide and an evaluator of the whole process and the pace setter (identifying objects) of teaching and learning. Also, advocated a child-centered education. They claimed that the child possessed within himself the potentialities for development, and that it's the task of the teacher to make these potentials develop by itself instead of imposing some external measures. These virtues are what educational field trip technique represents

which is contrary to what is obtainable with teaching and learning encounters with the use of lecture methods. Social studies teachers may be overloaded with facts and information but without appropriate dissemination methods to impart what is in him, his vast knowledge plus effort put forth will be nothing more than wasted resources. The traditional lecture method has been largely criticized for stifling interest and creativity in students thereby limiting academic achievement. The technique has been accused of being characterized by excessive dominance of the classroom teacher. The method more often than not does not give room for students' initiatives in learning. Students most of the time were mere passive listeners and their contributions to facts in the teaching and learning encounter is often neglected.

From the work of Susan A Egwu on field trips, in every human endeavour, every individual deserves to make a change in a positive direction. The change is usually to ensure that he improves on the present position for attainment in life. All these connote some form of achievement. In school, achievement is the level of attainment in a given discipline. It is the degree of attainment a student reaches after being subjected to a period of learning. Every discipline measures its own achievement in various ways and with various instruments. In school setting, tests and examinations are given to students to assess their achievement. Feedbacks are given to them in the form of scores and grades. A lot of factors

affect the achievement of biology students. These factors bear so much influence on the achievement of biology students. Over the years, research studies (Akande, Mogbo, Bello & Yaki, 2018; Duyilemi & Bolajoko, 2014; Joda, 2019; Osuafor & Okonkwo, 2013) have indicated that academic achievement of students who enroll in biology has not been encouraging. It is disheartening that candidates' performance in biology for five years; 2014 to 2018 are 56.17%, 57.42%, 61.68%, 55.57% and 55.10% respectively (WAEC Chief Examiner's reports, 2014 to 2018). The performance of students improved above average from 2014 to 2018 with the highest percentage of 61.68% in 2016. Although it was a remarkable improvement, this is still not good enough for a country like Nigeria that is in dire need of scientific knowledge such as biology. Agaba (2013) attributed the poor achievement in biology to lack of commitment to academics while Obi and Idoha (2013) added the dearth in science resources. Further, Agaba opined that for students to achieve better in biology, instructional materials should be used in the teaching of the subject because biology requires real objects and activities/experiments that can convert topics that seem imaginary to concretize for students' understanding. Students generally experience difficulties in understanding some concepts in biology.

Empirical studies on teaching and learning

Eze Nwosu (2011) on “out of classroom experience in the teaching and learning of Biology in Aguata L.G.A. of Anambra”. The researcher sampled four schools and a simple random method was used to collect data. Based on her findings, 90% of the students lack the knowledge of outside classroom experience. While 78% of the teachers revealed the factors militating against field trip as lack of finance, distance, attitude of parents etc. 70% of the students are of the opinion that ministry of education, curriculum planners and time-table planners as well should include field trips as a teaching method, both at the primary, secondary and tertiary institutions for effective teaching and learning of Biology as it enhances a firsthand experience. The researcher having done a comprehensive research opined that “allocation should be made from the ministry of education and school administration to finance and train teachers specifically for the purpose of field work”. More so, “field work centres should be established in strategic places, like places of biological importance with enough accommodation to accommodate states whenever they come for learning.

Summary of Literature Review

It has been scientifically stated that the use of field trips in educational training helps to effect the expected behavioral change in the students, therefore, the student should be taught with this most effective method of teaching the subject. Since field trip improves the method of teaching and learning, it will be

important for curriculum planners to make ‘field trip’ compulsory for all students at the primary, secondary and tertiary institutions. The second, Time-table planners should also map out enough time for field trips so that every teacher and students would benefit from this method. On the side of time-table planner, it should be designed in order for it not to clash with other subjects on the time table and parents should stop objecting to their children from going on field trips with the fear of them being injured, rather they should be encouraged and motivated. The problem militating against the use of field trips includes; finance, time table and denial of teachers opportunity to organize field trips.

The use of field trips has been revealed to help the students for easy exploration of their immediate environment. It gives them the ample opportunity to see things for themselves in their natural environment. It gives them new experience whenever they embark on field trips. It helps them to retain most of the things they are taught because they were able to see and touch those things.

The use of field trip due to its effectiveness needs to be institutionalized in all schools, though it may be faced with some problems.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH DESIGN AND PROCEDURE

The researcher in this chapter explains the methods, materials and processes to be employed in the conduction of the work. They include; research design, Area of the study, Population of the study, Sample and Sapling techniques, Instrument for data collection, Reliability of the instrument and Method of data collection.

Research Design

In this study, the researcher adopted a descriptive survey design which will be most suitable for collecting data from respondents and it will also be best used to organize, present and analyze data. For the purpose of investigating the effectiveness of field trips in teaching and learning of biology.

Area of the Study

The study was carried out in Ezinihitte Mbaise L.G.A using the senior secondary schools. Ezinihitte Mbaise is located on the Eastern part of Imo State; it is bounded on the south with Umuahia in Abia State. On the north, it is bound by Aboh Mbaise Local Government Area of Imo State, on the east it shares boundaries with Aboh Mbaise and Ahiazu Mbaise Local Government Area. From the West it is bounded by a river which separates the Area from Ngwa in Abia state. It has an access road from Obowo through Onicha Mbaise road.

It is popularly known for Agricultural production. It has an area of 113.7km² and a population of 232,400 at (2016) projection.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consists of all the secondary students in eleven (11) public secondary schools in Ezinihitte Mbaise Local Government Area. There are 4350 secondary school students in the schools used for the study.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample for this research consists of four hundred and eighteen secondary school students randomly selected from the 11 secondary schools in Ezinihitte Mbaise. The sampling techniques used in the study are the simple random sampling techniques which gives every student an equal chance of being selected, 10% of the students sampled was used for the work.

Instrument for Data Collection

Researcher made rating scale is the instrument for data collection for this study. The rating scale was made of two parts one is the personal information of the respondents and part two is the question to be answered. The purpose of the rating scale was to elicit the response of the respondents on the effectiveness of field trips in the teaching and learning of Biology. The instruments are in modified four (4) points Likerts format scale.

Agreed = A, Strongly Agreed = SA, Disagreed = D, Strongly Disagree = SD

Validation of Instrument

The instrument was validated by one specialist in education biology and one from measurement and evaluation. Their comments and input improved the quality of the instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument

Two reliability coefficients, coefficient of temporal stability and internal consistency of the instrument were determined. For the coefficient of temporal stability, a test and retest approach was used to establish the reliability coefficient of the instrument as 10 respondents from the secondary schools, who are not among the sample respondents, were used for the pilot study. The instrument was administered to them, their scores obtained and recorded as X values. In the next two weeks, the instrument was administered to them again, their scores were obtained and recorded as Y values. Then the Pearson moment correlation coefficient formula was used to establish the reliability coefficient of 0.80. Hence the instrument is said to be highly reliable over a small period of time.

Method of Data Collection

With the help of two research assistants, the instrument was administered to the respondents and collected on the sport toward instrument mortality

Method of Data Analysis

The frequency distribution of the scores was organized and tables used in analyzing the data collected in various categories since the questionnaire was based on sample nominal rating scale, simple arithmetic mean scores was used in analyzing the data, a mean score of 2.50 and above was deemed fit to accept the item, while any mean score below 2.5 was used to reject the item.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

In this chapter, the researcher presented the analysis of the data collected in respect to this study. Analysis of data was organized around the relevant research questions and presented in tables.

Research Question 1: To what extent are students exposed to the use of field trips in teaching and learning of Biology?

Table 1: Students exposure to Field trips

S/N	Item Statement	Mean Σfxf	Remark
1	Students have some knowledge of field trips through their teachers.	3.2	Accepted
2	Students read about field trips from magazines and journals.	3.1	Accepted
3	Students embark on field trips annually.	3.3	Accepted
4	Students have a little exposure to the field from their fellow students.	3.0	Accepted
Mean of item means		3.2	

The research question covers questions 1 to 4, from the table 1 above. The majority of the students opined that they have exposure to field trips through their teachers, magazines and journals while greater acquire awareness through

television. All the items received positive or accepted mean scores, meaning that the respondents agreed with the research question.

Research Question 2: What is the importance of embarking on a field trip?

Table2: Importance of embarking on a field trip.

S/N	Item Statement	Mean $\Sigma fx/f$	Remark
1	Field trips bring about effective teaching.	3.2	Accepted
2	Field trips bridge the gap between theory and practical.	3.1	Accepted
3	The field trip offers students a lasting experience of nature.	3.3	Accepted
4	Field trips help in recognition of organisms in their natural habitat.	3.0	Accepted
Mean of item means		3.2	

This research question covers questions 5-8 from the table 2 above. The majority of the students opined and strongly agreed that embarking on a field trip in teaching and learning in Biology is of great importance. All the items received positive or accepted mean scores, which mean that the respondents agreed with the research questions that embarking on a field trip is important.

Research Question 3: What are the problems that militate against the use of field trips in teaching and learning of Biology?

Table3: Problems of field trip

S/N	Item Statement	Mean Σfxf	Remark
1	Many teachers are not well equipped with the knowledge.	3.0	Accepted
2	Parents discourage their children from embarking on field trips because of fear of accidents.	2.8	Accepted
3	Lack of finance and distance militates against successful field trips.	3.0	Accepted
4	Lack of time factor in the school time table militates against effective field trips.	3.0	Accepted
Mean of item means		3.0	

From the above table, which covers item 9 to 12 of the rating scale, it is observed that research question 3 received a positive mean score of 4 which is a clear indication of acceptance of the fact that there are actually problems that militate against the use of field trips in teaching and learning of Biology.

Research question 4: What strategies can be effectively employed in the use of field trips in the teaching and learning of Biology?

Table4: Strategies to be used for effective field trip

S/N	Item Statement	Mean Σfxf	Remark
1	Areas of field the trip to make sure it is of field trip interest.	2.7	Accepted
2	Most environmental topics should be taught outside the classroom to arouse the students interest on field trips.	3.3	Accepted
3	Students should be provided with enough time to share general observations after lectures on field trips.	3.3	Accepted
4	The photographs of the field trip site should be shown to the students so as to motivate and arouse their interest towards field trips.	3.1	Accepted
Mean of item means		3.1	

The table above covers items 13 to 16 of the rating scale, research question 4 has a positive mean score. All the items received positive mean scores, meaning that the research questions of the strategies to be employed for effective field trips were accepted.

Summary of the Finding

Based on the data analyzed, 3.2 mean scores of the respondents accepted that students have exposure to field trips through their teachers, magazines and journals, while a greater number acquire the awareness through television.

From the research question two (2), the data collected showed that the use of field trip in teaching and learning in secondary schools is of great importance to students. Research question three (3) reveals that lack of time factor stipulated for the school activities which are the time table of the school and finance has been a constraint for effective use of field trips.

Conclusively, it is opined that inclusion of field trips in the curriculum and maximum awareness will go a long way for the effective teaching and learning of Biology.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS AND SUMMARY OF THE STUDY

Discussion of findings

The findings of this study with respect to the extent students are exposed to the use of field trips in teaching and learning biology. The mean score revealed that teaching methods used by teachers in the use of field trips for the effectiveness of field trip, includes; observation, discussion, lecture and demonstration methods and these methods have effect on the effectiveness of field trips in teaching and learning of Biology.

Nwabueze (2010) maintained that there is no substitute for the first hand information gained through observation of the living population in diverse situations and localities. He further said that the recognition of organisms in the outdoors is a long step toward the appreciation of nature and life itself. Tu see can be acquired through books, magazines, television, film shows, and internet. These can affect our interest and motivate our thinking just as ordinary food affects our body.

The findings of this study with respect to specific objective 2 revealed that there are importance of embarking on a field trip. The mean score from data analyzed supported the need for field trips. It creates an avenue for students to learn about different professions, ideas and opportunities when they travel outside their

own neighborhood. According to Iwu (2011) in agreement with the importance of field trip, opined that "field trip helps students to develop scientific skills of observation, recording, collecting and classifying.

The findings to this study with respect to specific objective 3 revealed the problems that militate against the use of field trip in teaching and learning of Biology, the findings shows that the negative attitude of the teachers due to distance, time considering fitting into the school time table may turn around to be problem especially if it comes from the school Administration. Iwu (2011) in agreement with specific objective 3 opined that one of the major problems encountered in field trips is financial. The result of the respondent indicates inadequate finance to have hindered the effectiveness of field trip in the teaching and learning of Biology.

The findings of this study with respect to specific objective 4 revealed the strategies that can be employed in the use of field trip in teaching and learning biology to be effective, this was analyzed in table four, from the result, 3.4 mean score of respondent indicated that there are ways of fighting against the factors that hinders the effectiveness of field trip.

Conclusion

The effectiveness of field trips in teaching and of Biology is absolutely necessary and should not be neglected.

Field trips help to stimulate interest and motivation in science, give meaning to learning and interrelationship, and personal social development. It is therefore recommended that field trips should be included in school curriculum and the government should provide allocation towards effective field trips.

Recommendation

The Recommendation from this study will be based on the findings derived after the whole data has been analyzed. The researcher came up with the following recommendation;

- The government should include field trips in the school curriculum, as it will help to develop a positive attitude towards field trips.
- Time table planners should allocate adequate time for field trips.
- Allocation should be made from the ministry of Education and school administration to finance and train teachers specifically for the purpose of effective field trips.

- School authorities should create more awareness on the importance of the field so that parents would not object to their children from going on field trips.
- Teachers should always relate most ecological topics to their natural environment.
- Schools should provide an in-service training programme for teachers to help them improve on this teaching method.

Educational Implication of the Study

It is obvious that field trips have an effect on teaching and learning. Inability of teachers to make good use of field trips in teaching and learning is really affecting the educational system. Field trip is targeted at unfolding some practice which are not taught or overlooked by the lecturer.

The neglect of field trips in most schools has a serious effect on the students because it does not give them the opportunity to explore their immediate environment. Field trips, according to some research work, will improve teaching and learning. It has been noted that "what is seen is more remembered than what is heard". So the use of this method will help the students to remember what they hear whenever they are called upon because they have the

opportunity to carry out some practical on most topics and this method enhances learning.

Some factors such as lack of finance, parents and teacher's attitude and distance have been found to militate against the use of the method in teaching and learning. Therefore, there is a need for these factors to be met in order to promote the effectiveness and goal of field trips. This agrees with the adage which says "seeing is believing"

Limitations of the Study

The researcher was confronted with numerous problems, and these problems to some extent limited the accuracy of this work, the problems are as follows:

- The researcher's zeal of the study was partly obstructed and hindered given the Monday sit-at-home observed in the East.
- Time and finance served as a constraint to carry out this study on a wider scope.
- Administrative and bureaucratic bottlenecks served as a serious limitation in the study.
- Inability of the respondents to return the questionnaire after collecting them from the researcher.

Suggestions for Further Studies

The researcher here suggested that this research work should be extended to all secondary schools in Imo State and other schools across the states of the federation as it will help students to have a lasting experience of nature. Also this research work should be extended to junior secondary, primary schools, even tertiary institutions in order to equip them with all the necessary facts and information.

Summary of the Studies

This research study was carried out to find out the effectiveness of field trips in the teaching and learning of biology in secondary schools in Ezinihitte Mbaise Local Government Area. The research was guided by four research questions from which a questionnaire was designed and administered to 436 students in public senior secondary schools in Ezinihitte Mbaise Local Government Area.

The analysis of the questions revealed that field trips provide students with permanent retention of knowledge.

Finally, based on the findings, some recommendations were made which include allocation of funds, creating awareness and making field trips compulsory at all levels of the educational system.

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APPENDIX I

Department Of Life Science Education,
Imo State University, Owerri,
Imo State

Dear respondent,

REQUEST TO COMPLETE A RATING SCALE

I am a final year student of the above mentioned institution and Department, currently undertaking research work on the topic; Influence of field trip in teaching and learning of biology among secondary school students in Ezinihitte Mbaise L.G.A.

You are kindly requested to give a sincere response to the items of instruments of the rating scale attached. The rating scale is designed to enable me to gather reliable data on the research work in order to meet the specific objectives of the study.

Thanks in anticipation for your cooperation.

Yours faithfully

Enyiason Commissioner C.

INSTRUMENT FOR DATA COLLECTION

Section A

Persona Data:

Name of School: _____

Gender: Mae [] Female []

Section B

You are required to react to each statement carefully and tick the appropriate option that best represents your view in the space provided.

The interpretation of the symbols are written below

Strongly agreed (SA)

Agreed (A)

Disagreed (D)

Strongly disagreed (SD)

Respond to these items as they affect you by ticking () in the appropriate column.

Research Question 1: To what extent are students exposed to the use of field trips in teaching and learning of Biology?

TABLE 1: Students exposure on field trip

S/N	Item Statement	Frequency responses of the respondents			
		SA	A	D	SD
1)	Students have some knowledge of field trips through their teachers.				
2)	Students read about field trips from magazines and journals.				
3)	Students embark on field trips annually.				
4)	Students have a little exposure to field trips from their fellow students.				

Research Question 2: What is the importance of embarking on a field trip?

S/N	Item Statement	Frequency responses of the respondents			
		SA	A	D	SD
5)	Field trip brings about effective teaching and learning to some environmental topics				
6)	Field trips bridge the gap between theory and practical.				
7)	The field trip offers students a lasting experience of nature.				
8)	Field trips help in recognition of organisms in their natural habitat.				

Research question 3: What are the problems that militate against the use of field trips in teaching and learning of biology?

S/N	Item Statement	Frequency responses of the respondents			
		SA	A	D	SD
9)	Many teachers are not well equipped with the knowledge of field trips.				
10)	Parents discourage their children from embarking on field trips because of fear of accidents.				
11)	Lack of finance and distance militate against successful field trips.				
12)	Lack of time factor in the school timetable militates against effective field trips.				

Research question 4: What are the strategies to be effectively employed in the use of field trip in teaching and learning of biology?

S/N	Item Statement	Frequency responses of the respondents			
		SA	A	D	SD
13)	The area of the field trip should be visited before the trip to make sure that it is of field trip interest.				
14)	Most environmental topics should be taught outside the classroom to arouse the students interest on field trips.				
15)	Students should be provided with enough time to share general observations after lectures on field trips.				
16)	The photographs of the field trip site should be shown to the students so as to motivate and arouse their interest towards field trips.				

APPENDIX II

Table. 1 Distribution of Total Population

S/N	NAMES OF SECONDARY SCHOOL	NO. OF SCHOOLS
1	Obama Secondary School	420
2	Chokoneze Technical School	200
3	Ife Secondary School	230
4	Mbaise Girls Secondary School Onicha	480
5	Ihitte Secondary School	380
6	Eziudo Secondary School	450
7	Itu Secondary School	275
8	Onicha Secondary School	410
9	Eziudo Secondary	490
10	Ime Onicha Comprehensive Secondary School	600
11	Obizi High School	415
	Total	4350

Sample Distribution

S/N	NAMES OF SECONDARY SCHOOL	NO. OF SCHOOLS	10% OF STUDENTS
1	Obama Secondary School	420	42
2	Chokoneze Technical School	200	20
3	Ife Secondary School	230	23
4	Mbaise Girls Secondary School Onicha	480	48
5	Ihitte Secondary School	380	38
6	Eziudo Secondary School	450	45
7	Itu Secondary School	275	28
8	Onicha Secondary School	410	41
9	Eziudo Secondary	490	49
10	Ime Onicha Comprehensive Secondary School	600	60
11	Obizi High School	415	42
	Total	4350	436

Research Question 1: To what extent are students exposed to field trips in the teaching of Biology?

Students exposure to Field trips

S/N	Item Question	Frequency responses of the respondents				Frequency responses multiplied by weight attached to the responses.				Mean		Remark
		SA	A	D	SD	SA×4	A×3	D×2	SD×1	∑fx	∑fxf	
1	Students have some knowledge of field trip through their teachers.	200	80	50	40	800	240	100	40	1,180	3.2	Accepted
2	Students read about field trip from magazines and journals.	160	70	35	40	640	210	70	40	960	3.1	Accepted
3	Students embark on field trip annually.	170	75	20	30	680	225	40	30	975	3.3	Accepted
4	Students have a little exposure to the field from their fellow students.	90	140	40	35	360	420	80	35	895	3.0	Accepted

Research Question 2: What is the importance of embarking on a field trip?

Importance of embarking on a field trip.

S/N	Item Question	Frequency responses of the respondents				Frequency responses multiplied by weight attached to the responses.				Mean		Remark
		SA	A	D	SD	SA×4	A×3	D×2	SD×1	Σfx	Σfx/f	
1	Field trips bring about effective teaching.	200	80	50	40	800	240	100	40	1,180	3.2	Accepted
2	Field trips bridge the gap between theory and practical.	160	70	35	40	640	210	70	40	960	3.1	Accepted
3	Field trips offer students a lasting experience of nature.	170	75	20	30	680	225	40	30	975	3.3	Accepted
4	Field trips help in recognition of organisms in their natural habitat.	90	140	40	35	360	420	80	35	895	3.0	Accepted

Research Question 3: What are the problems that militate against the use of field trips in teaching and learning of Biology?

Table4.3: Problems of field trip

S/N	Item Question	Frequency responses of the respondents				Frequency responses multiplied by weight attached to the responses.				Mean		Remark
		SA	A	D	SD	SA×4	A×3	D×2	SD×1	Σfx	$\frac{\Sigma fx}{f}$	
1	Many teachers are not well equipped with the knowledge.	120	100	40	30	480	300	80	30	890	3.0	Accepted
2	Parents discourage their children from embarking on field trips because of fear of accidents.	100	80	60	55	400	240	120	55	815	2.8	Accepted
3	Lack of finance and distance militates against successful field trips.	118	81	59	40	472	243	118	40	873	3.0	Accepted
4	Lack of time factor in the school time table militates against effective field trips.	150	40	90	20	600	120	180	20	920	3.0	Accepted

Research question 4: What strategies can be effectively employed in the use of field trips in the teaching and learning of Biology?

Strategies to be used for effective field trip

S/N	Item Question	Frequency responses of the respondents				Frequency responses multiplied by weight attached to the responses.				Mean		Remark
		SA	A	D	SD	SA×4	A×3	D×2	SD×1	Σfx	Σfx/f	
1	Areas of field the trip to make sure it is of field trip interest.	70	110	60	50	280	330	120	50	780	2.7	Accepted
2	Most environmental topics should be taught outside the classroom to arouse the students' interest on field trips.	180	75	25	20	720	225	50	20	1015	3.3	Accepted
3	Students should be provided with enough time to share general observations after lectures on field trips.	170	80	22	22	680	240	44	22	986	3.3	Accepted
4	The photographs of the field trip site should be shown to the students so as to motivate and arouse their interest towards field trips.	105	20	26	420	450	450	40	26	936	3.1	Accepted

APPENDIX III

TABLE 4.1:

Grand total = = = 3.2

TABLE 4.2:

Grand total = = = 3.2

TABLE 4.3:

Grand total = = = 2.9

TABLE 4.4:

Grand total = = = 3.1